

A description of the universal solution to the Kepler problem

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Abstract

The main objective of this article is to present details of an approach that develops universal formulas to solve the Kepler problem. The equations of motion and the energy integral of the two-body problem are derived. By applying the Sundman transformation to regularize the dynamics of the problem, we can eliminate a singularity and obtain two regularized equations of motion. Using families of Battin and Stumpff functions determined from solutions of regularized differential equations, we have derived formulas that are universally applicable and free from numerical indeterminacy. This includes the expression for the radial distance, the Kepler's universal equation, the closed-form expressions for the coefficients f , \dot{f} , g and \dot{g} , and the expressions for the orbit state variables.

1 Introduction

The Kepler problem is known as the prediction problem [1], initial value problem [7], or the orbit propagation problem [2]. This problem is a particular case of the classical two-body problem, which aims to determine the future location of a celestial body in orbit from the position and velocity vectors at a specific instant of time. For this purpose, the Kepler problem is often applied in Astrodynamics, because its solution is the basis for planning and simulating space missions.

The solution to the Kepler problem is achieved using a transcendental equation that relates the mean and true anomalies with time, known as Kepler's equation. However, when solving this equation for each type of conic section, that is, ellipse, hyperbola, and parabola, we face computational difficulties, mainly in calculating interplanetary trajectories where the orbit undergoes drastic changes. Therefore, a uniform approach is required to solve this problem.

The uniform or universal approach is a widely used technique to determine the trajectory of a spacecraft in an orbital maneuvering simulation environment. This technique employs a regularization method using the Sundman transformation [3], where the time is replaced by an independent variable χ , also known as a universal variable or generalized anomaly. Using this variable, it is possible to obtain a solution to the two-body problem valid for elliptical, hyperbolic, and parabolic orbits, including circular and rectilinear orbits.

Pitkin [4] and Everhart & Pitkin [6] applied the universal approach in the dynamics of the two-body problem to obtain a singularity-free solution to the Kepler problem. Thus, using the regularizing transformation given by expression

$$\sqrt{\mu}dt = rd\chi, \tag{1}$$

where μ is the gravitational parameter and the universal anomaly χ is defined by the relation with the true (ν), eccentric (E), and hyperbolic (H) anomalies:

$$\chi = \begin{cases} \sqrt{p}(\tan(\nu/2) - \tan(\nu_0/2)), \\ \sqrt{a}(E - E_0), \\ \sqrt{-a}(H - H_0). \end{cases} \tag{2}$$

Pitkin proposed the application of Eq.(1) into the equation of relative motion of the secondary body. This approach allowed him to obtain a equation of motion regular at $r = 0$. Everhart & Pitkin explored this concept. Nevertheless, they developed a method in which the equation of motion and integral of energy were both regularized. This allowed the derivation of two equations of motion regular at $r = 0$. Through the integration of the regularized equations, the authors derived universal formulas to solve the Kepler problem. This included an expression for the radial distance, the universal Kepler's equation, the expressions for the orbit state variables at a reference epoch t , and the closed-form expressions for the coefficients f , \dot{f} , g , and \dot{g} based on the independent variable χ . However, the universal formulas presented a singularity when the semi-major axis of the orbit reached zero. As a consequence, the authors utilized a universal auxiliary variable to ensure that the universal formulas would exhibit regular behavior. Thereafter, Battin [7] presented a universal solution to the Kepler problem using a family of universal functions. The families were obtained by solving a linear second-order differential equation with a constant coefficient, which was regularized by the Sundman transformation using Eq.(1). Similar to Pitkin [4] and Everhart & Pitkin [6], Battin derived universal formulas to solve the Kepler problem and utilized a universal auxiliary variable to create a new set of universal functions to ensure that the universal formulas would also exhibit regular behavior.

The main objective of this study is to describe a method that develops a set of formulas to solve the Kepler problem for any conic section (ellipse, hyperbola, or parabola) using the approaches adopted by Pitkin [4], Everhart & Pitkin [6] and Battin [7]. Our study model is described by a two-body system in which a primary body of mass m_1 , is fixed at the origin of the inertial frame of reference and a secondary body of mass m_2 , orbiting around the central body. The motion of the secondary body is supposed to be in a planar Keplerian orbit. Thus, in Section 2, we derive the equation of motion and the expression of the energy integral for the two-body problem. To avoid the formation of a singularity resulting from collisions between celestial bodies. We present a classic regularization method based on the Sundman transformation. By applying this technique, we can obtain two regularized differential equations: a second-order nonlinear scalar equation and a third-order linear vector equation. In Section 3, the universal Battin functions are derived from the solutions of regularized differential equations. Therefore, universal formulas free from numerical indeterminacy at $r = 0$ were obtained. These formulas include the expression for the radial distance, the Kepler's equation, the closed-form expressions for the coefficients \mathcal{F} , \mathcal{G} , \mathcal{F}' and \mathcal{G}' , and the expressions for the position and velocity vectors. We also apply an inverse transformation so that universal formulas can be numerically integrated over time. The closed-form expressions for the coefficients f , \dot{f} , g , and \dot{g} are then obtained. However, universal formulas still exhibit numerical indeterminacy when the semi-major axis of the orbit of the secondary body approaches zero. Thus, we apply a universal auxiliary variable to construct the Stumpff functions to eliminate the numerical indeterminacy. Then, we present a formulation to solve the Kepler's equation in Section 4. Finally, an algorithm for solving the universal Kepler problem is presented in Section 5.

2 The Regularized Two-Body Problem

2.1 The Equation of Motion

Consider the case of a secondary body of mass m_2 moving in a force field of gravitational attraction due to a primary body of mass m_1 , located at the center of the inertial frame of reference. From Newton's laws of motion and gravitation, the equation of relative motion of the secondary body is given by

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}} + G(m_1 + m_2) \frac{\mathbf{r}}{r^3} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where $G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}$ is the universal gravitational constant and \mathbf{r} is the position vector of the secondary body relative to the primary body.

2.2 The Energy Integral

The expression of the energy integral is obtained by taking the dot product of the vector $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$ with Eq.(3), so that

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}} + \frac{G(m_1 + m_2)}{r^3} \dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \mathbf{r} = 0 \quad (4)$$

or, consequently

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dt} (\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}) - \frac{G(m_1 + m_2)}{r^2} \frac{dr}{dt} = 0. \quad (5)$$

Integrating Eq.(5), we have

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{(\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})}{2} - \frac{G(m_1 + m_2)}{r}, \quad (6)$$

where \mathcal{E} is a constant of integration that represents the energy of the two-body system.

2.3 Regularizing Transformation

The equation of relative motion of the secondary body reveals a singularity at $r = 0$, as shown in Eq.(3). According to Pitkin [4], the search for a valid solution in the vicinity of a singularity is only possible if the point can be regularized, such that the singularity becomes regular. To regularize Eq.(3) and prevent the singularity generated by collisions between the bodies, we use the Sundman transformation given by expression

$$\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)} dt = r d\chi. \quad (7)$$

Applying the chain rule to the variable r , we have that

$$\frac{dr}{d\chi} = \frac{dr}{dt} \frac{dt}{d\chi}. \quad (8)$$

Hence, we obtain the regularizing derivative formulas

$$\frac{dr}{d\chi} = \frac{r}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}} \frac{dr}{dt} = \frac{r\dot{r}}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}} = \frac{\mathbf{r} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}, \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d^2 r}{d\chi^2} = \frac{d}{d\chi} \left(\frac{dr}{d\chi} \right) = \frac{r(\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}} + \mathbf{r} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{r}})}{G(m_1 + m_2)}. \quad (10)$$

Combining Eqs.(3) and (6) with Eq.(10), we then obtain a second-order scalar nonlinear differential equation

$$r'' + \sigma r = 1, \quad (11)$$

where the superscript $''$ denotes the second derivative with respect to the variable χ and the variable σ is given by

$$\sigma = -\frac{2\mathcal{E}}{G(m_1 + m_2)} = \frac{2}{r} - \frac{(\dot{\mathbf{r}} \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}})}{G(m_1 + m_2)} = \frac{1}{a}. \quad (12)$$

We now proceed with the regularization technique by directly applying the Sundman transformation in Eq.(3) to find

$$\mathbf{r}'' - \frac{r'\mathbf{r}'}{r} + \frac{\mathbf{r}}{r} = 0. \quad (13)$$

Multiplying Eq.(13) by variable r and differentiating the result with respect to the variable χ . We replaced the variable r'' by Eq.(11) and arrive at the third-order vector linear differential equation

$$\mathbf{r}''' + \sigma\mathbf{r}' = 0. \quad (14)$$

3 The Universal Formulas

3.1 The Battin Functions

Taking Eq.(11) in its linear form

$$r'' + \sigma r = 0. \quad (15)$$

We develop the solution of Eq.(15) by substituting a power series

$$r = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} a_k \chi^k, \quad (16)$$

so that we arrive at the solution

$$r = a_0 Y_0(\chi; \sigma) + a_1 Y_1(\chi; \sigma), \quad (17)$$

where a_0 and a_1 are two arbitrary scalar constants, and $Y_0(\chi; \sigma)$ and $Y_1(\chi; \sigma)$ are universal functions or universal Battin functions given by

$$Y_0(\chi; \sigma) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{(\sigma\chi^2)^k}{(2k)!}, \quad (18)$$

$$Y_1(\chi; \sigma) = \chi \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{(\sigma\chi^2)^k}{(2k+1)!}. \quad (19)$$

For any n non-negative integer, the n -th function of such a sequence is easily seen to be

$$Y_n(\chi; \sigma) = \chi^n \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{(\sigma\chi^2)^k}{(2k+n)!}. \quad (20)$$

From Eq.(20), we obtain the recursive formula

$$Y_n(\chi; \sigma) + \sigma Y_{n+2}(\chi; \sigma) = \frac{\chi^n}{n!}, \quad (21)$$

where

$$Y_{n+2}(\chi; \sigma) = \chi^{n+2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{(\sigma\chi^2)^k}{(2(k+1)+n)!}. \quad (22)$$

By differentiating Eqs.(18) and (20), we obtain the derivative formulas

$$\frac{dY_0(\chi; \sigma)}{d\chi} = -\sigma Y_1(\chi; \sigma), \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{dY_n(\chi; \sigma)}{d\chi} = Y_{n-1}(\chi; \sigma), \quad \text{for } n > 0. \quad (24)$$

We have already shown that Eq.(17) is the general solution of Eq.(15). However, it also represents the homogeneous solution of Eq.(11). The general solution of Eq.(11) is then obtained by determining its particular solution and adding it to its homogeneous solution. Therefore,

$$r = a_0 Y_0(\chi; \sigma) + a_1 Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + \frac{1}{\sigma}. \quad (25)$$

Differentiating Eq.(25) and using the derivative formulas given in Eqs.(23) and (24), we get then

$$r' = -a_0 \sigma Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + a_1 Y_0(\chi; \sigma). \quad (26)$$

Applying the initial conditions $r(0) = r_0$ and $r'(0) = r'_0$, where χ is taken to be zero at t_0 , in Eqs.(25) and (26), so that $Y_0(0; \sigma) = 1$ and $Y_1(0; \sigma) = 0$. Then, eliminating the variable σ by evaluating Eq.(11) at $\chi = 0$, and using the recursive formula given in Eq.(21). We arrived at the equation

$$r = r_0 + r'_0 Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + r''_0 Y_2(\chi; \sigma). \quad (27)$$

Substituting Eq.(27) in the integrated form of the Sundman transformation

$$\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)} \int_{t_0}^t dt = \int_0^\chi r d\chi \quad (28)$$

and using the derivative formula given in Eq.(24). We can obtain a transcendental equation analogous to the universal Kepler's equation equals to

$$\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0) = r_0 \chi + r'_0 Y_2(\chi; \sigma) + r''_0 Y_3(\chi; \sigma). \quad (29)$$

The variable r''_0 is eliminated from Eqs.(27) and (29) by evaluating Eq.(11) at $\chi = 0$. Therefore, we obtain

$$r = r_0(1 - \sigma Y_2(\chi; \sigma)) + r'_0 Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + Y_2(\chi; \sigma), \quad (30)$$

$$\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0) = r_0(\chi - \sigma Y_3(\chi; \sigma)) + r'_0 Y_2(\chi; \sigma) + Y_3(\chi; \sigma). \quad (31)$$

Integrating Eq.(14), we get a second-order vector nonlinear differential equation

$$\mathbf{r}'' + \sigma \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{C}, \quad (32)$$

where \mathbf{C} denotes a constant vector. The search for the solution of this equation follows an approach similar to that used for Eq.(11). Its homogeneous solution is similar to Eq.(15), however its particular solution is \mathbf{C}/σ . The general solution of Eq.(32) is then obtained by adding its particular solution to its homogeneous solution. Thus,

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{b}_0 Y_0(\chi; \sigma) + \mathbf{b}_1 Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + \frac{\mathbf{C}}{\sigma}, \quad (33)$$

where \mathbf{b}_0 and \mathbf{b}_1 are two arbitrary vector constants.

Differentiating Eq.(33) and using the derivatives formulas given in Eqs.(23) and (24), we get

$$\mathbf{r}' = -\mathbf{b}_0\sigma Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + \mathbf{b}_1 Y_0(\chi; \sigma). \quad (34)$$

Applying the initial conditions $\mathbf{r}(0) = \mathbf{r}_0$ and $\mathbf{r}'(0) = \mathbf{r}'_0$, where χ is taken to be zero at t_0 , in Eqs.(33) and (34). Then, eliminating the variable σ evaluating Eq.(32) at $\chi = 0$, and using a recursive formula given in Eq.(21). We arrive at the equation

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_0 + \mathbf{r}'_0 Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + \mathbf{r}''_0 Y_2(\chi; \sigma). \quad (35)$$

Differentiating Eq.(35) and using the derivative formulas given in Eqs.(23) and (24), we have

$$\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{r}'_0 Y_0(\chi; \sigma) + \mathbf{r}''_0 Y_1(\chi; \sigma). \quad (36)$$

The variable \mathbf{r}''_0 is eliminated from Eqs.(35) and (36) by evaluating Eq.(13) at $\chi = 0$. Therefore, we obtain

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_0 \mathcal{F} + \mathbf{r}'_0 \mathcal{G}, \quad (37)$$

$$\mathbf{r}' = \mathbf{r}_0 \mathcal{F}' + \mathbf{r}'_0 \mathcal{G}', \quad (38)$$

where the coefficients \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{G} are given by

$$\mathcal{F} = 1 - \frac{Y_2(\chi; \sigma)}{r_0}, \quad (39)$$

$$\mathcal{G} = Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + \frac{r'_0 Y_2(\chi; \sigma)}{r_0}. \quad (40)$$

We can determine the expressions of the coefficients \mathcal{F}' and \mathcal{G}' by differentiating Eqs.(39) and (40) with respect to the variable χ . Thus, using a derivative formula given in Eq.(24), we get

$$\mathcal{F}' = -\frac{Y_1(\chi; \sigma)}{r_0}, \quad (41)$$

$$\mathcal{G}' = Y_0(\chi; \sigma) + \frac{r'_0 Y_1(\chi; \sigma)}{r_0}. \quad (42)$$

These equations are known as universal formulas in the sense that they are valid for all types of orbits and void of singularities. For this reason the $Y_n(\chi; \sigma)$ functions are referred to as universal functions.

3.2 Inverse Transformation

In this subsection, an inverse transformation is performed on the universal formulas to eliminate the terms that contain derivatives with respect to the independent variable χ . Consequently, we expect that universal formulas can be numerically integrated over time. Thus, evaluating Eq.(9) at $t_0 = 0$, where $\chi = 0$, so Eqs.(30) and (31) are rewritten, respectively, as

$$r = r_0(1 - \sigma Y_2(\chi; \sigma)) + \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}} Y_1(\chi; \sigma) + Y_2(\chi; \sigma), \quad (43)$$

$$\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0) = r_0(\chi - \sigma Y_3(\chi; \sigma)) + \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}} Y_2(\chi; \sigma) + Y_3(\chi; \sigma). \quad (44)$$

Eliminating the second term in Eqs.(40) and (42) using Eqs.(31) and (30), respectively. Then, performing an inverse transformation to variables r' and r'_0 in Eqs.(37) and (38) using Eq.(7), we obtain the state vector expressions

$$\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{r}_0 f + \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0 g, \quad (45)$$

$$\dot{\mathbf{r}} = \mathbf{r}_0 \dot{f} + \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0 \dot{g}, \quad (46)$$

where the closed-form expressions for the coefficients f , g , \dot{f} and \dot{g} are given by

$$f = 1 - \frac{Y_2(\chi; \sigma)}{r_0}, \quad (47)$$

$$g = (t - t_0) - \frac{Y_3(\chi; \sigma)}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}, \quad (48)$$

$$\dot{f} = -\frac{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}{r r_0} Y_1(\chi; \sigma), \quad (49)$$

$$\dot{g} = 1 - \frac{Y_2(\chi; \sigma)}{r}. \quad (50)$$

3.3 The Stumpff Functions

The Battin functions are, of course, related to the elementary functions but the particular relations depend on whether the orbit of the secondary body is a parabola $a = 0$, an ellipse $a > 0$, or a hyperbola $a < 0$. According to Eq.(12), when the semi-major axis of the orbit of the secondary body is zero, then $\sigma = 0$. This implies that universal formulas yields numerical indeterminacy. Hence, we introduce a universal auxiliary variable [7]

$$\psi = \sigma \chi^2, \quad (51)$$

so that a new family of functions, known as the Stumpff functions $\mathcal{S}_n(\psi)$, can be defined in terms of the $Y_n(\chi; \sigma)$ functions as

$$\chi^n \mathcal{S}_n(\psi) = Y_n(\chi; \sigma), \quad (52)$$

where

$$\mathcal{S}_n(\psi) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{\psi^k}{(2k + n)!}. \quad (53)$$

From the general expression of the Stumpff function, we arrive at the recursive formula

$$\mathcal{S}_n(\psi) + \psi \mathcal{S}_{n+2}(\psi) = \frac{1}{n!}, \quad (54)$$

where

$$\mathcal{S}_{n+2}(\psi) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{\psi^k}{(2(k+1) + n)!}. \quad (55)$$

By differentiating Eq.(53), we find the derivative formula

$$\frac{d\mathcal{S}_n(\psi)}{d\psi} = \frac{1}{2\psi} (\mathcal{S}_{n-1}(\psi) - n\mathcal{S}_n(\psi)), \quad \text{for } n = 1, 2, \dots \quad (56)$$

From here, the Battin functions in the universal formulas will be replaced by the definition of the

Stumpff function, as shown in Eq.(52). Therefore, the closed-form expressions for the coefficients f , g , \dot{f} and \dot{g} are now given respectively by

$$f = 1 - \frac{\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi^2}{r_0}, \quad (57)$$

$$g = (t - t_0) - \frac{\mathcal{S}_3(\psi)\chi^3}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}, \quad (58)$$

$$\dot{f} = -\frac{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}{rr_0}(1 - \sigma\mathcal{S}_3(\psi))\chi, \quad (59)$$

$$\dot{g} = 1 - \frac{\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi^2}{r}. \quad (60)$$

The expression for the radial distance and the universal Kepler's equation become, respectively

$$r = r_0(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)) + \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_3(\psi))\chi + \mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi^2, \quad (61)$$

$$\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0) = r_0(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_3(\psi))\chi + \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi^2 + \mathcal{S}_3(\psi)\chi^3. \quad (62)$$

The second and third Stumpff functions are related to the elementary functions as follows:

$$\mathcal{S}_2(\psi) = \begin{cases} (\cosh \sqrt{-\psi} - 1) / -\psi & \psi < 0, \\ (1 - \cos \sqrt{\psi}) / \psi & \psi > 0, \\ 1/2 & \psi = 0, \end{cases} \quad (63)$$

and

$$\mathcal{S}_3(\psi) = \begin{cases} (\sinh \sqrt{-\psi} - \sqrt{-\psi}) / \sqrt{-\psi^3} & \psi < 0, \\ (\sin \sqrt{\psi} - \sqrt{\psi}) / \sqrt{\psi^3} & \psi > 0, \\ 1/6 & \psi = 0, \end{cases} \quad (64)$$

where $\psi = 0$, $\psi > 0$, and $\psi < 0$ are related to the parabolic, elliptical, and hyperbolic orbits, respectively.

4 Solution of the Kepler's Equation

The solution of the Kepler problem is achieved by first finding a value of χ corresponding to the time t and then by finding the orbit state variables $(\mathbf{r}, \dot{\mathbf{r}})$ corresponding to χ . The value of χ is determined using the universal Kepler's equation with a numerical iteration method (e.g., Newton's method). Thus, from Eq.(62), we form the function

$$F(\chi) = r_0(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_3(\psi))\chi + \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi^2 + \mathcal{S}_3(\psi)\chi^3 - \sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0). \quad (65)$$

The derivative of Eq.(65) is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dF(\chi)}{d\chi} &= r_0(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_3(\psi)) - r_0 \left(\frac{d\psi}{d\chi} \mathcal{S}_3(\psi) + \psi \frac{d\mathcal{S}_3(\psi)}{d\psi} \frac{d\psi}{d\chi} \right) \chi + \\ &\quad \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}} \left(\frac{d\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)}{d\psi} \frac{d\psi}{d\chi} \chi^2 + 2\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi \right) + \frac{d\mathcal{S}_3(\psi)}{d\psi} \frac{d\psi}{d\chi} \chi^3 + 3\mathcal{S}_3(\psi)\chi^2. \end{aligned} \quad (66)$$

Using the derivative formula given in Eq.(56), we arrive at the derivative of the function $F(\chi)$ as

$$\frac{dF(\chi)}{d\chi} = r_0(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_2(\psi)) + \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{\sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}}(1 - \psi\mathcal{S}_3(\psi))\chi + \mathcal{S}_2(\psi)\chi^2, \quad (67)$$

which is equivalent to

$$\frac{dF(\chi)}{d\chi} = \sqrt{G(m_1 + m_2)}\frac{dt}{d\chi} = r \quad (68)$$

where r is given in Eq.(61).

Thereafter, Eqs.(65) and (67) are then replaced in a recursive sequence, so that the value of χ is updated at each iteration from an initial value of χ_0 , as will be described in the next section.

5 Summary

Given the initial (t_0) and final (t) times of an epoch, the initial orbital elements of the secondary body ($a, e, I, \Omega, \omega, \nu$), in addition to the masses of the primary (m_1) and secondary (m_2) bodies. The steps to solve the Kepler problem are as follows:

1. Convert the initial orbital elements of the secondary body into the state vectors ($\mathbf{r}, \dot{\mathbf{r}}$).
2. For the initial estimate of χ , we use the expression

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_0 = & \sqrt{\mathcal{G}(m_1 + m_2)}\frac{(t - t_0)}{r_0} - \frac{\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0}{2r_0^3}\sqrt{\mathcal{G}(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0)^2 + \\ & \frac{(\mathbf{r}_0 \cdot \dot{\mathbf{r}}_0)^2}{2r_0^5}\sqrt{\mathcal{G}(m_1 + m_2)}(t - t_0)^3 - \dots, \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

as recommended by D'Amario & Synnott [5].

3. After obtaining χ_i from the previous step, calculate $F(\chi_i)$ and $F'(\chi_i)$. And then calculate an updated value of χ using the expression

$$\chi_{i+1} = \chi_i - \frac{F(\chi_i)}{F'(\chi_i)}, \quad (70)$$

where $F(\chi_i)$ and $F'(\chi_i)$ are given in Eqs.(65) and (67), respectively.

4. If $|F(\chi_i)/F'(\chi_i)|$ exceeds the chosen tolerance (e.g., $\epsilon = 10^{-8}$), return to step 3 with the updated value of χ and continue iterating until χ can be improved to the desired accuracy. However, if $|F(\chi_i)/F'(\chi_i)|$ is less than the specified tolerance, then χ is accepted as the solution, and the subsequent steps are executed using the updated value of χ .
5. Compute the values of f and g using the Equations (57) and (58), respectively.
6. Calculate the vector \mathbf{r} using Equation (45).
7. Compute the derivatives of \dot{f} and \dot{g} using Equations (59) and (60), respectively.
8. Calculate the vector $\dot{\mathbf{r}}$ using Equation (46).

6 Final Remarks

We developed a detailed solution to Kepler's problem using the approaches adopted by Pitkin [4], Everhart & Pitkin [6] and Battin [7]. In the first part of this work, we applied the Sundman

transformation to regularize the dynamics of the two-body problem, thus obtaining two regularized equations of motion. From the solution of the regularized equations using the Battin functions, followed by the application of the inverse transformation and the use of the Stumpff functions, we obtained universal formulas free of numerical indeterminacy to solve the Kepler problem for any conic section (ellipse, hyperbola, or parabola). This included the expression for the radial distance, the Kepler's universal equation, the closed-form expressions for the coefficients f , \dot{f} , g and \dot{g} , and the expressions for the orbit state variables. Finally, we presented the procedure for solving the Kepler problem using universal Kepler's equation.

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